

KINETICS OF INTERFACIAL REACTIONS IN FIBER-REINFORCED Ti₃Al + Nb MATRIX COMPOSITES

S. M. Jeng and J.-M. Yang
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of California, Los Angeles, CA 90024

ABSTRACT

The interfacial reaction characteristics between various fibers and the Ti₃Al + Nb matrix were studied over the temperature range of 700 °C to 1050 °C with time ranging from 2-200 hours. Monolayer unidirectional composites with continuous SCS-6, Sigma, B₄C/B and SiC/B fibers were consolidated using a diffusion bonding technique. The microstructure and chemical compositions of the fiber/matrix reaction zone was characterized by electron microscopy and electron probe microanalysis. The growth kinetics of the fiber/matrix reaction zone such as the reaction constant and activation energy were also determined for each composite system.

INTRODUCTION

The titanium aluminides, both Ti₃Al (α_2) and TiAl (γ), are promising materials for light-weight, high temperature structural applications [1-11]. They have a higher stiffness and strength than conventional titanium alloys at both room and elevated temperatures, combined with lower density and good high temperature oxidation resistance. They also have adequate creep strength to a much higher temperature than do conventional titanium alloys. The incorporation of high strength and stiffness continuous fibers into the titanium aluminide can further improve their mechanical properties. Potential applications of these novel composite materials include advanced structures for hypersonic aircraft, space vehicles, turbine engine components, etc. However, it is well-known that excessive fiber/matrix interfacial reactions occur during composite consolidation and service at high temperature. The formation of brittle intermetallic compounds at the interface will severely affect the mechanical properties of the composites. In order to control and design the interface, it is necessary to understand the nature and the extent of the fiber/matrix interaction.

Some pioneering work has been conducted to characterize the reaction zone microstructure and growth kinetics, and assess the effect of reaction zone thickness on the thermo-mechanical behavior of the composites [12-16]. The objective of this paper is to present some of our recent investigation of the interface reaction characteristics between various fibers and the Ti₃Al + Nb (α_2 + β) matrix, with emphasis on the kinetics of the interaction.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Four types of continuous fibers synthesized by chemical vapor deposition were used in the present investigation: SCS-6, Sigma-SiC, B₄C/B and SiC/B. Ti-24 Al-11 Nb was supplied in thin sheet form from Timet Corporation with a thickness of 9 mils. The unidirectional, monolayer composite panels were consolidated by the vacuum diffusion bonding technique. The microstructure and the chemical compositions of the interface was characterized using optical and scanning electron microscopy, as well as electron probe microanalysis (EPMA). In order to study the reaction kinetics, the composite specimens were vacuum (10^{-3} torr) encapsulated in a quartz

tube followed by isothermal exposure over the temperature range of 700 - 1050 °C for 2 to 200 hours. After isothermal exposure, the specimens were prepared for metallographic examination. The thickness of the reaction zone was measured by using high magnification SEM micrographs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Microstructural Analysis of Reaction Zone

The scanning electron micrographs of the interfacial reaction zone for SCS-6, Sigma, B₄C/B and SiC/B fiber-reinforced Ti₃Al + Nb composites are shown in Fig. 1. It is clear that all of the fibers react with Ti₃Al + Nb matrix to form complex reaction products during consolidation and

Fig. 1 The interfacial reaction zones of (a) SCS-6/Ti₃Al + Nb, 900 °C/8 hours, (b) Sigma/Ti₃Al + Nb, 900 °C/8 hours, (c) SiC/B-Ti₃Al + Nb, 900 °C/4 hours, (d) B₄C/B-Ti₃Al + Nb, 950 °C/4 hours.

thermal exposure. The elemental distributions across the fiber/matrix interface analyzed by EPMA for SCS-6/Ti₃Al + Nb and B₄C/B-Ti₃Al + Nb composites are shown in Fig. 2. Microprobe analyses show that the reaction products between the fibers and the Ti₃Al + Nb matrix are more complicated than those of the Ti or Ti-6Al-4V matrix. The reaction zone of the SCS-6/Ti₃Al + Nb composite has been identified as composed of two different sublayers: (Ti, Nb)C_(1-x), (Ti,Nb,Al)₅Si₃ adjacent to the fiber; (Ti,Nb)₃AlC and (Ti,Nb,Al)₅Si₃ adjacent to the matrix. [16]. Significant amount of porosities resulting from the unbalance transport of constituents in the fiber and the matrix were found at either the matrix/reaction zone or reaction zone/fiber interface. The formation of voids will lead to the weakening of the interfacial bond strength [15]. Also, a thin layer of β depleted region adjacent to the reaction zone was observed in all four composite systems. The mechanism of formation of the β -depleted zone adjacent to the reaction zone is not well understood yet. However, it will create a large brittle zone (α_2) which might severely affect the properties of the composites. The detailed microstructure and chemical compositions across the reaction zone of each composite analyzed by EPMA and TEM can be found in ref. [13-16].

B. Reaction Kinetics

The increase in reaction zone thickness as a function of the square root of time for four types of fiber-reinforced Ti₃Al + Nb composites at 950 °C and 1038 °C are shown in Fig. 3. These plots show that for several temperatures the growth of the reaction zone was linear with the square root of time. This indicates that the reaction is mainly controlled by diffusion, and hence the reaction zone thickness follows a parabolic growth law. The temperature dependence of reaction rate k can be expressed by the Arrhenius equation: $k = k_0 \exp(-Q/2RT)$, Q is the activation energy of the reaction process. Thus, by plotting the logarithm of the rate of reaction zone thickness, in $\mu\text{ms}^{-1/2}$, vs the reciprocal of the absolute temperature, the activation energy of the reaction process for each composite system can be calculated. The activation energy and the rate constant for the growth of the reaction zone determined from the Arrhenius plot are listed in Table I. The SCS-6/Ti₃Al + Nb system has the highest activation energy (64.6 Kcal/mole), while the B₄C/B-Ti₃Al + Nb system has the lowest activation energy (40 Kcal/mole). It is evident that the extent of interfacial chemical reaction depends on the thermodynamic compatibility of the components and the fiber surface chemistry.

The kinetics data indicate that, in all four types of composites, the growth rate of the interfacial reaction zone is too fast, especially at high temperature. A thick layer of brittle intermetallic compounds formed at the interface only after a short-term thermal exposure. It has been shown that the strain-to-fracture of the reaction products is less than that tolerated by fiber, so that crack initiation starts in the reaction zone under longitudinal tensile loading [17]. The formation of cracks in the thick reaction zone leads to immediate failure of the reinforcing fiber. Thus, the fiber failure is no longer controlled by the intrinsic fiber defects, but by the brittle reaction layer surrounding the fiber. This will certainly lead to severe property degradation and premature failure of the composite. Therefore, methods to improve the interfacial compatibility and to reduce the rate of growth of the reaction zone occurring at the interface are essential for the development of useful fiber-reinforced Ti₃Al + Nb composites.

SUMMARY

- (1) SCS-6, Sigma, B₄C/B, and SiC/B fibers reacted extensively with Ti₃Al + Nb to form multilayer reaction products during consolidation and extended isothermal exposure.
- (2) The fiber/matrix interfacial reaction is diffusion-controlled, and the fiber surface chemistry affects the development of the reaction zone and the distribution of the reaction products.
- (3) Development of a diffusion barrier coating or a new reinforcement which is chemically more compatible with the Ti₃Al + Nb matrix is needed.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 The thickness of the reaction zone as a function of the square root of time for various fiber-reinforced $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}$ composites at (a) $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, (b) $1038\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table II The k_0 and Q for Various $Ti_3Al + Nb$ Matrix Composites [14, 15, 18]

	k_0 (cm sec ^{-1/2})	Q (Kcal/mole)
Sigma/ $Ti_3Al + Nb$	0.278	51.9
SCS-6/ $Ti_3Al + Nb$	3.156	64.6
B4C/B- $Ti_3Al + Nb$	0.0144	40.0
SiC/B- $Ti_3Al + Nb$	0.139	47.1
SCS-6/ $Ti-6Al-4V$	0.41	59.3

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REFERENCES

1. H. A. Lipsitt, in High-Temperature Ordered Intermetallic Alloys, C. C. Koch, C. T. Liu, and N. S. Stoloff, ed., MRS, 1985, V. 39, p. 351.
2. S. R. Schuon, and A. P. Druschitz, Journal of Metal, 39 (1987) 36.
3. P. L. Martin, M. G. Mendiratta and H. A. Lipsitt, Metallurgical Transactions, 14A (1983) 2170.
4. A. Loiseau, and A. Lasalmonie, Materials Science & Engineering, 67 (1984) 163.
5. H. A. Lipsitt, D. Shechtman, and R. E. Schaftrick, Metallurgical Transactions, 11A (1980) 1369.
6. R. J. Kearns, Metallurgical Transactions, 15A (1984) 1721.
7. M. G. Mendiratta, and H. A. Lipsitt, Journal of Materials Science, 15 (1980) 2985.
8. S. M. L. Sastry and H. A. Lipsitt, Metallurgical Transactions, 8A (1977) 1543.
9. P. L. Martin, H. A. Lipsitt, N. T. Nuhfer, and J. C. Williams, in Titanium 80: Science and Technology, H. Kimura and O. Izumi ed., TMS-AIME, 1980, p. 1245.
10. R. Strychor, J. C. Williams, and W. A. Soffa, Metallurgical Transactions, 19A (1988) 225.
11. A. Khataee, H. M. Flower, and D. R. F. West, Journal of Materials Engineering, 10 (1988) 37.
12. P. K. Brindly, in High-Temperature Ordered Intermetallic Alloys, N. S. Stoloff, C. C. Koch, C. T. Liu, and O. Izumi, ed., MRS, 1987, V. 81, p. 351.
13. P. K. Brindley, P. A. Bartolotta, and S. J. Klima, NASA-TM 100956, 1988.
14. J.-M. Yang and S. M. Jeng, Metallurgical Transactions, 1988, in press.
15. S. M. Jeng, W. Kai, C. J. Shih, and J.-M. Yang, Materials Science and Engineering, 1988, in press.
16. S. F. Baumann, P. K. Brindley and S. D. Smith, Metallurgical Transactions, 1988, in press.
17. P. Soumelidis, J. M. Quenisset, R. Naslain, and N. S. Syoloff, Journal of Materials Science, 21 (1985) 895.
18. P. Martineau, R. Pailler, M. Lahaye, and R. Naslain, Journal of Materials Science, 19 (1984) 2479.